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The Probable Mechanism of Condensation of Some Reported Heteropoly Niobates and Tantalates in Basic Medium

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THE general principle of condensation process^{1,2} of heteropoly acids is, that the maintenance of acid medium is a must. The mechanism of such condensation process has been established³ successfully through oxobridge idea. But our previous reports^{3,4} reveal a very interesting phenomenon that the condensation of heteropoly niobates and tantalates may take place in basic medium also. The formations of 12-heteropoly Niobotungstate(VI)³ and tantalato tungstate(VI)⁴ have been marked in basic medium^{3,4,5} at some certain pH values 11.5 and 11.6 respectively. Dale et al⁶ has prepared sodium 12-niobotantalatomanganate(VI) at pH 12. In this communication attempts have been made to elucidate some probable mechanism for such types of basic medium condensation process in heteropoly niobates and tantalates.

The example of condensation or polymerization process in basic medium, i.e., in presence of OH ions or groups are numerous in chemical literature. The formation of polynuclear cobalt and chromium complexes through hydroxyl bridge, have been discussed⁷. The closed packed three dimensional crystalline growth of various metal hydroxides through OH groups or ions have been elaborately discussed⁸. There are examples of organic polymers also, wherein, OH groups or ions behaves as catalyst in polymerisation processes. The reaction mechanism in condensation process in organic and inorganic compounds in presence of OH groups or ions may broadly be classified as follows :

(i) Typical structure of OH ions where there is no hydrogen bonding. Examples—aluminium silicates, hydroxides of rare earths, etc.

(ii) Typical coordination of OH group with hydrogen bonding (O-H...O) amongst groups of OH or water molecules. Examples—ice, Conc. H₂SO₄.

(iii) Typical coordination of OH groups without hydrogen bonding⁹. Directed bonds are formed when the groups are attached to different metal atoms, leading to more open packing. In such cases OH-OH distance is generally more than 2.80 to 2.90 Å. The polarization of OH group is not ruled out.

(iv) Typical catalytic behaviour of OH group as in the base catalysed aldol condensation.

For a comparison and prediction with the existing data which is also very scanty, it may be argued that the possibility of the points (iii) and (iv) may be useful to interpret the formation of niobotungstate(VI) in basic medium. A reference to a X-ray examination of isopoly dodecatungstate compound has confirmed the formula to be Na₁₀·[W₁₂O₃₆(OH)₁₀].23H₂O. This shows that the hydrogen present in the compound is not as H⁻ but as OH⁻. The existence of OH group has been further confirmed by n.m.r. spectra⁹. Taking this analogy it may be concluded, that the heteropoly salts of niobotungstate(VI) and tantalatungstate(VI) may contain OH group and this is possible in reaction where there is hydroxyl groups. This prediction needs confirmation by detailed studies of X-ray and n.m.r. spectra. The next possibility of formation is the presence of OH group according to the observation no. (iv). It may be predicted that OH behaves as catalyst and the resultant arrangement might be the polyhedra of the oxides of niobium and tantalum by the elimination of H₂O molecule. Indications may be had from the reports of X-ray studies on isopoly anion [Nb₆O₁₉]⁸⁻, wherein Lindqvist¹⁰ and others pointed out a sort of projection pattern from niobium and oxygen.

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